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Abstract. Research purpose was to assess the possibilities of creating and transplanting a cornea to hu- mans.

Materials and methods: reviewed the current publications of Russian and foreign authors on such bases as PubMed, Medline, e-Library. Were studied information about the methods of keratoprosthetics, the structure of the keratoprostheses used today, modern developments in the field of replacing the donor cornea with an equivalent created by using 3D bioprinting technologies, as well as the possibility of transplanting keratoxenografts to human, have been analyzed.

Results and their discussion: The cornea is a complex structure of an eye. It consists of 5 layers: epithelium, Bowman's layer, stroma, Descemet's membrane and endothelium. Some authors also distinguish 6-th layer - pre-Descemet's membrane. Each of these layers has their own functions. Cornea is a transparent, avascular and highly innervated tissue. Its primary functions are to transmit and refract light entering the eye and to protect the eye. Today there is an acute problem of lack of donor corneas, as a result of which the development of analogs is required, that can completely replace the human cornea. Keratoprostheses are widely used all over the world, some types of which are entirely made of synthetic materi- als and show good engraftment, as well as a high percentage of vision restoration in patients. However, their use is limited to strict indications. The use of modern technologies in the field of tissue engineering - 3D-bioprinting allows you to create the cornea in artificial conditions. However, selection of material for bio-ink is difficult. Such material must have sufficient mechanical strength, biocompatibility, transparency, bioinertness, suitable biodegradability, and must comply with clinical requirements. Collagen and silk fibroin have been found to be the most suitable materials. However, collagen is not strong enough, therefore it is combined with alginate, and silk fibroin is not sufficiently similar to the proteins of the human extracellular matrix. Nevertheless, the printed structures have shown good vitality, and in the future, they are planned to be engrafted in humans. Another ex- perimental method that allows replacing the donor cornea is

the use of kerat xenografts taken from a pig. However, in the experiments carried out, it was found that not all prostheses were engrafted, and those that were engrafted required further keratoplasty or keratoprosthesis.

Conclusions: today there are prostheses that can replace the donor cornea - keratoprosthesis, but their use is strictly limited and is decided in each case individually. Developments in the field of bioprinting of the cornea have shown that it is possible to synthesize a model of the cornea, but requires careful selection of materials, and existing models show good results when engrafted in rabbits. Kerat xenografts can be transplanted in urgent cases. Such operations are effective as organ-preserving ones. Thus, to date, there is no anatomical and functional replacement for the donor cornea, but there is a lot of research in this area.

Keywords: donor cornea, keratoprosthesis, keratoprosthesis, 3D bioprinting, kerat xenograft.

Аннотация. *Цель исследования* – оценить возможности создания и трансплантации роговицы человеку. *Материалы и методы исследования.* Проанализированы актуальные публикации российских и зарубежных авторов на ресурсах *PubMed, Medline, E-library*. Критерием выбора были материалы, содержащие информацию о способах кератопротезирования, строении используемых сегодня кератопротезов, современных разработках в области трансплантации донорской роговицы эквивалентом, созданным с использованием технологий 3D-биопринтинга, а также возможность пересадки кератоксеноимплантов. *Результаты и их обсуждение.* Роговица – это сложная структура зрительного анализатора человека, состоящая из 5 слоев: эпителий, Боуменова мембрана, строма, Десцеметова мембрана, эндотелий. Некоторые авторы также выделяют 6 слой – пре-Десцеметова мембрана. Каждый из этих слоев выполняет свою функцию. Роговица – прозрачная, богато иннервируемая, аваскулярная ткань. Она является важным компонентом преломляющей системы зрительного аппарата глаза, также выполняет защитную функцию. Сегодня остро стоит проблема нехватки донорских роговиц, вследствие чего требуется разработка аналогов, способных полностью замещать роговицу человека. Широкое применение во всем мире получили кератопротезы, некоторые виды которых полностью состоят из синтетических материалов и показывают хорошую приживляемость, а также высокий процент восстановления зрения у пациентов. Однако их применение ограничивается строгими показаниями. Использование современных технологий в области тканевой инженерии – 3D-биопринтинга позволяет создать роговицу в искусственных условиях. Сложность заключается в подборе материала для

био-чернил. Материал должен отвечать следующим критериям: иметь достаточную механическую прочность, биосовместимость, прозрачность, биоинертность, подходящую биоразлагаемость и должен соответствовать клиническим требованиям. Установлено, что наиболее подходящими материалами являются коллаген и фиброин шелка. Коллаген отличается недостаточной прочностью, поэтому его комбинируют с альгинатом; а фиброин шелка в свою очередь недостаточно схож с белками внеклеточного матрикса человека. Тем не менее напечатанные структуры согласно литературным данным показали хорошую жизнеспособность и в перспективе планируется их практическое применение. Еще одним экспериментальным методом, позволяющим заменить донорскую роговицу, является использование кератоксеноимплантов взятых от свиньи. В проведенных экспериментах установлено, что не все протезы приживались, а прижившиеся требовали проведения в дальнейшем кератопластики или повторного кератопротезирования. **Выводы.** В настоящее время существуют протезы, способные заменить донорскую роговицу – кератопротезы, однако их использование строго ограничено и решается в каждом случае индивидуально. Разработки в области биопечати роговицы глаза показали, что синтезировать модель роговицы возможно, однако требуется тщательный подбор материалов, а уже существующие модели показывают хорошие результаты при приживлении их кроликам. Кератоксеноимпланты возможно пересаживать в urgentных случаях. Такие операции эффективны как органосохраняющие. Таким образом, на сегодняшний день не разработано соответствующей донорской анатомической и функциональной замены донорской роговице, но ведется множество исследований в этой области.

Ключевые слова: донорская роговица, кератопротезирование, кератопротез, 3D-биопринтинг, кератоксеноимплант.

Introduction. The cornea is a complex multilayered structure of the visual analyzer. It performs a number of important functions, namely, it provides mechanical protection for the eye and, at the same time, is one of the main refractive systems of the visual organ, therefore, it cannot be completely removed in case of its pathologies. Damage or pathology of the cornea carries a high risk of developing blindness or a significant decrease in visual acuity. In 2010, there were 200,000 visually impaired people in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Keratoplasty is included in the mandatory list of surgical procedures for the rehabilitation of such patients. However, due to an acute shortage of transplants, they are placed on the "Waiting List for Donor Corneas". Every year, approximately 17 thousand patients are included on such lists, while only 1 in 70

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patients in need receives a donor cornea. In 72% of patients, vision improves after keratoplasty, further demonstrating the need for a larger number of grafts. Despite the lack of replacement of the donor cornea, keratoprotheses are widely used worldwide today for severe damage. These prostheses are made of artificial materials that integrate well into the eye, but their use is limited by strict indications.

To address the problem of corneal transplantation for improving vision when donor corneas are limited, numerous studies are being conducted aimed at creating artificial corneas. For this purpose, modern tissue engineering techniques such as 3D bioprinting are ideal. This method allows for layer-by-layer reproduction of human structures. With the correct selection of bio-inks, it is possible to create a graft that closely resembles the native cornea. In recent years, the possibility of transplanting such a cornea into humans has been explored. The described transplant is based on collagen, which is characterized by good biocompatibility with human tissue, the absence of an immune response, and the material is transparent, which is necessary for the refraction of light. Another material that can be used for bioprinting is silk fibroin, obtained from silkworm cocoons. This protein has all the properties suitable for the synthesis of the cornea. A completely different direction is the use of animal corneas for transplantation to humans. Clinical trials have been conducted on the implantation of a pig keratoxen implant in humans. The aim of the study was to evaluate the feasibility of creating and transplanting a cornea into humans.

Materials and methods: We analyzed relevant publications by Russian and international authors over the past 10 years, including those published in PubMed, Medline, and E-library. The selection criteria included materials containing information on keratoprosthetic techniques, the structure of currently used keratoprotheses, current developments in replacing donor corneas with equivalents created using 3D bioprinting technologies, and the feasibility of keratoxin implants.

Results and discussion. The cornea is a transparent, avascular, well-innervated structure of the eye, located in its anterior part. It is the most important element of the refractive system of the visual apparatus. In addition, it performs a protective function, preventing the impact of harmful environmental factors on the eye. The cornea occupies approximately 1/16 of the area of the outer shell of the eye. It has the appearance of a convex-concave lens, with the concave part facing backward. It is the first tissue through which light enters the eye and is directed to the pupil. The cornea is divided into 5 layers: epithelium, Bowman's membrane, stroma, Descemet's membrane, and endothelium. Some authors also distinguish a 6th layer - the pre-Descemet's membrane [14]. Among them, the epithelium, stroma, and endothelium are the cellular layers, and Bowman's membrane, pre-Descemet's membrane, and Descemet's membrane are the acellular layers. The anterior layer is a multilayered

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squamous nonkeratinizing epithelium that prevents tear fluid, toxins, and microorganisms from entering. The basal cell layer of the corneal epithelium is the only one with the ability to mitose, which allows it to quickly renew itself and not leave opacities with minor injuries. Between the epithelium and the stroma is Bowman's membrane, which consists mainly of collagen types I and III, as well as inclusions of collagen fibers types V and VI. It contains numerous pores for the passage of nerve fibers. The thickness of this layer decreases with age and does not regenerate with injury and its removal. The stroma makes up 80-85% of the thickness of the cornea. It consists of a cellular component – keratocytes, which synthesize its extracellular component – collagen. The stroma determines such properties of the cornea as transparency, stretchability, strength, and stability. The pre-Descemet's membrane consists mainly of type I collagen, but also contains type VI collagen, which is organized in 5-8 layers with elastic fibers originating in the peripheral parts of the cornea and in the limbus region. This structure is important for corneal attachment. Descemet's membrane consists mainly of type IV collagen. Its thickness increases with age and provides mechanical protection of the endothelium [22]. The corneal endothelium is a single layer of specialized hexagonal cells capable of mitosis. However, they lose their ability to divide immediately after the final formation of the endothelium. The number of cells in this layer of the cornea decreases with age as the cell area increases. This layer prevents the destruction of the stroma by maintaining a certain water balance—78% water—through the K^+ , Na^+ , and adenosine triphosphate pump, which moves water ions from the hypotonic stroma to the hypertonic aqueous humor. This is essential for nourishing all layers of the cornea, as it is an avascular structure. Therefore, the primary criterion for selecting donor corneas is the density of endothelial cells, which are capable of providing the transplant with nutrients.

Corneal pathologies account for 17-25% of all eye diseases. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), there are over 50 million people worldwide in need of a corneal transplant. In 2010, the WHO also estimated that 39 million people suffer from blindness, 12% of which are due to corneal pathology.

A corneal transplant is a microsurgical procedure during which a damaged corneal area is replaced with a donor graft. This procedure is called keratoplasty. The goal of this surgical treatment is to improve vision deteriorating due to diseases affecting the cornea or injuries. The shortage of cadaveric donor corneas is a pressing issue and has remained relevant for several years. The creation of an artificial cornea would solve the problem of its shortage for all patients in need. However, the development of such a transplant faces several challenges, including the toxicity and allergenicity of the materials, as well as the impossibility of fully restoring the original corneal geometry and optical functions of the eye. Nevertheless, grafts based on

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synthetic materials—keratoprotheses—are used in clinical practice worldwide. Their use is limited by strict indications, which include recurrent graft rejection, category 4-5 opacity, herpetic keratitis, Stevens-Johnson syndrome, cicatricial pemphigoid, etc. The idea of implanting a transparent artificial, alloplastic material into a opacity to restore vision—keratoprosthesis—belongs to Guillaume Pellier de Quengsi, who in 1789 proposed inserting a glass plate into a hole made in the opacity. J. Nussbaum was the first to perform experimental corneal prosthetics in 1853. His intralamellar glass plate remained in the cornea of a rabbit for three years. He also attempted to insert rock crystal prostheses, shaped like cufflinks, into a hole made in a leukoma, but all of them were soon rejected. In the USSR, keratoprotheses were first performed by V.P. Filatov in 1936.

Keratoprosthesis surgery is performed in two stages. In the first stage, the affected cornea is separated, and a support plate of the prosthesis, shaped to match the curvature of the cornea, is implanted between the layers. Peripheral openings are created in the support plate to allow the separated cornea to fuse and the keratoprosthesis to be secured. The center of this structure contains an opening for the optical portion of the prosthesis, which is closed with a plug at this stage of the surgery. Two to three months pass between surgeries. In the second stage of keratoprosthesis, trepanation of the clouded portions of the cornea above the opening for the optical portion of the prosthesis is performed. The plug is removed, the inner layers of the cornea are excised, and the optical cylinder of the keratoprosthesis is inserted. To prevent the optic portion from becoming fused, it has a projection on the anterior and posterior surfaces. Non-penetrating keratoprosthesis is also possible and is prescribed for bullous dystrophic lesions of the cornea. This condition is accompanied by severe tissue swelling, the formation of blisters on the corneal surface, and severe pain. Unlike penetrating keratoprosthesis, this procedure prevents excessive moisture absorption in the anterior chamber and the anterior layers of the cornea. After its implementation, corneal swelling and epithelial bullosity are reduced, relieving the patient of pain. Non-penetrating keratoprosthesis improves vision only for a short period of time, as the posterior layers of the cornea remain edematous, while the anterior layers lose their transparency and thicken. Penetrating keratoplasty is indicated for these patients in the future. Today, such prostheses as the Boston keratoprosthesis (B-KPP) types I and II, the Fedorov-Zuev keratoprosthesis, the Osteo-odonto-keratoprosthesis, and the AlphaCor are widely used worldwide. One of the most commonly used is the B-KPP type I, due to its simple design and ease of use. In Russia, the Fedorov-Zuev keratoprosthesis, manufactured by the Eye Microsurgery Company, is most commonly used.

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B-Kppo was developed by Dr. Claes Dohlman in 1968. It has been modified several times and was approved by the US Food and Drug Administration in 1992. More than 12,000 implantations have been performed worldwide. There are two types of B-Kppo, which differ in their structure and indications for use. B-Kppo type I is more often used for patients with sufficient tear production, providing lubrication of the ocular surface. Type II is used for patients with very dry and keratinized ocular surface. Type I consists of an anterior and posterior plate made of polymethyl methacrylate. The anterior plate consists of a cap, which acts as an optical lens, where the dioptric power is calculated by substituting the value of the axial length of the eye, and a cylinder on which the donor cornea is placed, and then the posterior plate. The posterior plate has 16 holes necessary to maintain corneal metabolism and hydration. B-Kppo Type II differs from Type I by an additional optical element, which is implanted after eyelid suturing and remains on the ocular surface. Another difference is that B-Kppo Type I provides a field of view of up to 60 degrees, while Type II provides a narrower field of view—40 degrees.

The Fedorov-Zuev keratoprosthesis consists of a non-porous tantalum plate support base and a cylindrical optical element made of Dacryl plexiglass, threaded to a sleeve rigidly attached to the base. A drawback of the device is its low engraftment rate due to the imperfections of the base. The impermeable base plate separates the anterior and posterior corneal layers over a large area, disrupting their anatomical and physiological relationship, disrupting trophic conditions, and leading to the development of aseptic necrosis. In 1963, Benedetto Strampelli developed the Osteo-odonto-keratoprosthesis, the supporting base of which consists of alveolar tissue previously taken from the recipient. Despite the complexity of the procedure, which requires several surgeries spread over several months, Osteo-odonto-keratoprosthesis is becoming increasingly popular, as it has a relatively high success rate and allows for the restoration of vision in cases where other methods are inapplicable for a variety of reasons.

To date, there is no universal prosthesis that could completely replace a donor cornea and solve the problem of graft shortages. Much research is being conducted in this area, aimed at finding materials that could reproduce the structural and functional properties of the native human cornea. Such compounds must have sufficient mechanical strength, biocompatibility with the potential recipient's tissues, transparency, bioinertness, suitable biodegradability, and must meet clinical requirements.

The development of artificial materials for corneal flap replacement has been underway for over fifty years. In 1966, a group of scientists led by Barraquer J. performed one of the first intrastromal implantations using celloidin lenses. Due to

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pronounced neovascularization of the cornea, these lenses did not find application in ophthalmology. In 1994, Ferrata de Chunha proposed polymethyl acrylate for intracorneal implantation. It had many positive characteristics: high biocompatibility, a refractive index close to that of the cornea, ease of processing, and adequate plasticity and elasticity. However, it was found that polymethyl acrylate, when implanted, caused visual aberrations and impaired twilight vision in the postoperative period, limiting its use in clinical practice.

Gelatin films were considered another promising material due to their good biocompatibility and bioinertness. Russian ophthalmologists M.M. Dronov and V.S. Karanov In 2008, this material was tested as an intrastromal implant in the treatment of various corneal dystrophies; however, its use required the use of interrupted sutures, which led to the formation of induced corneal astigmatism.

A corneal transplant with the closest properties and shape to a corneal transplant can be obtained using modern tissue engineering technologies such as 3D bioprinting. This method allows for the layer-by-layer application of biomaterial with micrometer accuracy according to a predetermined template, previously obtained by scanning living tissue or the structure of the human body.

When using this technology to create an artificial cornea model, studies describe the use of collagen for bio-inks, as it is the main extracellular component of the corneal stroma. Type I collagen is most commonly used; it is inexpensive to manufacture and promotes good nerve growth in the tissue. However, this material is not strong and elastic enough to maintain the desired shape. To address this issue, hydrogels, which are widely used in tissue engineering due to their low toxicity, similarity to the extracellular matrix, and tunable biophysical properties, have been added to the bio-ink. In studies, structures printed with such inks demonstrated high mechanical stability, which increased with increasing alginate concentration in the bio-ink. This composition provides a favorable environment necessary for the growth of keratocytes, which are used as the cellular component of the synthesized cornea. These cells, in turn, are obtained from human cadaveric corneal tissue and cultured under specific conditions. Furthermore, the cell morphology depends on the rigidity of the material in which the cell cultures are placed. The rigidity of the material must be such that, when transferred to the surface of the keratocytes, they are able to align the collagen so that its structure is as close as possible to that of the human cornea.

Other studies have suggested the possibility of replacing collagen with silk fibroin, obtained from the cocoon of the *Bombyx mori* silkworm. This protein, like collagen, is widely used in tissue engineering and regenerative medicine due to its ability to virtually not provoke an immune response, controlled degradation rate, and mechanical properties suitable for 3D bioprinting. In experiments, silk fibroin was used

as a basis for bio-ink and showed good results. Structures printed using this material are capable of supporting the multilayer structure of the epithelium, provide a good medium for the growth of human corneal epithelial cells, and are also characterized by sufficient ingrowth of nerve fibers. However, in its pure form, it is inferior to human collagen due to the lack of natural extracellular matrix proteins. Nevertheless, silk fibroin films implanted in rabbits for six months did not produce an immune response and remained transparent. However, the engraftment of such transplants in humans has not yet been carried out.

An advantage of 3D bioprinting is that the composition and structure of the created corneal equivalent can be modified, allowing for the reproduction of anatomical features of the cornea, such as Bowman's membrane or the limbal zone. However, research in this area currently requires further analysis of biocompatibility after human transplantation and, equally importantly, the ability of the graft to functionally replace the cornea.

To date, there have been cases of human transplantation of a keratogen implant taken from a healthy, freshly slaughtered pig raised in special conditions. This cornea is removed along with the scleral rim, treated with a cryoprotectant, and preserved in liquid nitrogen, followed by vacuum drying. After passing technical inspection, the keratogen implant is sterilized using radiation. The results of the studies showed that this keratoplasty method is effective in urgent cases as an organ-preserving surgery that alleviates the inflammatory process. This group of patients is recommended for subsequent keratoplasty or keratoprosthesis, depending on the severity of the corneal damage.

Conclusions. A significant percentage of people worldwide suffer from bilateral blindness due to corneal pathology, and most of them require corneal replacement surgery to restore vision. Many patients are forced to spend extended periods on a waiting list for donor corneas. Keratoprostheses based on synthetic materials have been developed for patients with severe corneal transparency defects; however, these are installed strictly according to indications and are not suitable for keratoplasty. To address the shortage of donor corneas, 3D bioprinting can be used. This method allows for the layer-by-layer creation of a predetermined structure with micrometer precision. However, the complexity of the method lies in the selection of substrates for the bio-ink. These components must meet the following requirements: sufficient mechanical strength, biocompatibility, transparency, bioinertness, suitable biodegradability, and create a favorable environment for cell proliferation. This is why all research into creating artificial corneas is in the development stage. Existing studies have established that collagen and silk fibroin are the most suitable materials. However, using collagen requires the addition of alginate to the substrate to increase mechanical strength, and

silk fibroin lacks similarity to human extracellular matrix proteins. However, both materials have demonstrated good viability, and clinical trials for human corneal implantation based on them are planned. Porcine corneal transplantation is another experimental method, but results have shown that it is only suitable as an organ-preserving procedure necessary to relieve ocular inflammation and requires subsequent keratoplasty or keratoprosthesis. Therefore, there is currently no optimal polymer material for the treatment of various corneal diseases, nor a keratoxin implant capable of fully replacing donor material. The choice of a particular polymer is determined by the need to balance clinical and functional efficacy with the risk of postoperative complications and should be decided on an individual basis.

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